

Additional file 8. Table of included pediatric studies.

Study	n	Prevalence of sepsis	Timing of test	PCT Cut-off (ng/mL)	Inclusion Criteria	Outcome Diagnosis	Sensitivity %	Specificity %	LR +	LR -	DOR	Ln(DOR)	St error (ln(DOR))
<i>Calò Carducci 2014</i>	64	64	0h	0.55	SIRS	MC or CR	0.878	0.739	3.4	0.16	20.4	3.02	0.67
<i>Groselj-Grenc 2009</i>	36	67	0h	0.28	SIRS	CR	0.833	0.750	3.3	0.22	15.0	2.71	0.86
			24h	0.65			0.810	0.880	6.8	0.22	31.3	3.44	1.04
<i>Pourakbari 2010</i>	158	79	0h	0.5	SIRS	MC	0.800	0.359	1.2	0.56	2.2	0.81	0.60
				2			0.680	0.744	2.7	0.43	6.2	1.82	0.56
				10			0.520	0.821	2.9	0.59	5.0	1.60	0.58
<i>Simon 2008</i>	64	39	24h	0.5	SIRS	CR	0.649	0.469	1.2	0.75	1.6	0.49	0.34
				2.5			0.439	0.796	2.1	0.71	3.0	1.11	0.37
				5			0.298	0.888	2.7	0.79	3.4	1.21	0.43

CR, Chart review; DOR, diagnostic odds ratio; LR +, positive likelihood ratio; LR -, negative likelihood ratio; MC, Microbiologically confirmation; PCT, procalcitonin; SIRS, systemic inflammatory response syndrome.